

Project number: 730879

Project acronym: INFRAFRONTIER2020

Project title: Development of mouse mutant resources for functional analyses of human diseases - Enhancing the translation of research into innovation

D8.1 Systemic late onset phenotyping analysis of 5 mutant mouse lines

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Call Information

Provision of access to the following infrastructure:

INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure

Description of the infrastructure

Name of the infrastructure: INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure

Legal name of organisation operating the infrastructure: Medical Research Council (MRC Harwell), Helmholtz Zentrum München (HMGU)

Location (town, country) of the infrastructure: Munich (Germany) is the seat of the INFRAFRONTIER legal entity. Harwell, UK is the location of the MRC Harwell, and Munich, Germany, is the location of the Helmholtz Zentrum München operating the German Mouse Clinic (GMC), both of whom are providing this Transnational Access service

Web site address: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/late-onset-systemic-phenotyping-ageing-pipeline>

Annual operating costs of the infrastructure (€): MRC Harwell, 7.022.305 €

Helmholtz Zentrum München GmbH (German Mouse Clinic GMC), 4.077.923 €

Description of the infrastructure:

MRC Harwell and the GMC provided Transnational Access to researchers across Europe to submit mouse lines to their comprehensive phenotyping service. Five researchers used this Transnational Access which builds upon the research performed in the EC-funded EUMODIC and INFRAFRONTIER-I3 projects. The centres are fully equipped with state-of-the-art research instrumentation to facilitate comprehensive phenotypic analyses covering a wide range of physiological functions including cardiovascular, neuro-behaviour and metabolism, and expertise in detailed pathology assessments. Routinely, all phenotyping activities are performed in a high-throughput capacity, as a service to support internal programs or for the wider scientific community. I2020 WP8 will offer access to this unique infrastructure.

Access unit:

The free-of-charge access unit offered covered the production of a cohort and a comprehensive first line phenotyping. The phenotyping was performed at several ages so that late onset of disease could be measured and / or the progression of disease with age

Services currently offered by the infrastructure:

MRC Harwell and the GMC are partners in the IMPC and perform first-line phenotyping of around 140 lines, and 100 lines respectively, per year. This is funded by the UK MRC, the NIH, and by the Helmholtz Association. Phenotyping is performed according to the standardised SOPs within an agreed pipeline of tests. The tests and pipeline for the late onset phenotyping is shown below. The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project opens up new areas to users, in that phenotyping will be performed at later ages allowing exploration

of late onset disease. There are few laboratories equipped to offer this comprehensive phenotyping and access to it at later ages makes it a unique opportunity. The **INFRAFRONTIER2020 proposal opened up new research areas to users with phenotyping performed at later ages allowing exploration of late onset disease.** There are few laboratories equipped to offer this comprehensive phenotyping and access to it for aged mice makes it a unique opportunity to study ageing-related phenotypes.

IMPC late onset pipeline and tests under discussion

Description of work

Modality of access under this proposal:

Calls for free of charge access units for phenotyping were published via the INFRAFRONTIER website (www.infrafrontier.eu). INFRAFRONTIER has a large database of contacts within the scientific community that were directly emailed to advertise the service. They also distributed call information to the project partners via email. Two calls were published overall, one in the first year and one in the second year of the proposed INFRAFRONTIER2020 project. Two TA units were offered in each call. The publication dates of the calls will ensure that phenotype data can be delivered within the project lifetime. Dedicated service request forms for submitting TA applications will be provided on the INFRAFRONTIER website.

The users must be from institutions of eligible countries: EU Member States and Associated States

- Applications will be subjected to a review procedure by the INFRAFRONTIER Evaluation Committee. This is a mixed panel consisting of external experts to assess

scientific excellence of project proposals and infrastructure operators who assess feasibility of project proposals

- Successful applicants must submit mouse mutant lines to the EMMA repository
- The phenotyping data will be made publicly available through a phenotyping database. For knock-out lines we will use the IMPC portal at www.mousephenotype.org
- The phenotyping facility will provide health status requirement to accept animals
- A service agreement will be established between the user and the phenotyping facility describing: the sanitary conditions for mice or embryo importation, the number of mice to be generated (sex, genotype, age, genetic background), the phenotyping assays that will be performed, and the deliverables (raw data, data analysis, reporting.)

The **access unit** consisted of a comprehensive, customizable first line phenotyping of a mutant line with appropriate controls. Possible starting materials were breeding pairs or frozen embryos. Data was planned to be delivered within 24 months of receipt of the mouse materials.

Support offered under this proposal:

Users benefited from access to the infrastructure, technical expertise and phenotyping work performed within the MRC and GMC mouse clinic. In addition, they were given support by MRC Harwell and GMC to analyse and interpret the results. MRC Harwell also suggested additional phenotyping tests that they can do further describe the phenotypes. As well as the phenotyping service, MRC Harwell has a number of research groups ranging from the investigation of the underlying genetics in disorders of sex development, the relationship between disrupted circadian rhythms and psychiatric disease, the role of cilia in development and disease, genetics of hearing loss and otitis media, type 2 diabetes and bioinformatics. Researchers from these groups could provide scientific input to the customisation of the pipelines used and analysis and interpretation of the results.

Mutant mouse lines were provided by the selected applicant either as breeding pairs or frozen embryos. MRC Harwell bred the cohorts required for the pipelines, used the IMPC late onset phenotyping pipelines and performed any relevant additional tests such as: adult and embryonic Imaging (MRI, μ CT, NMR), Circadian Rhythm, Sleep, Cognition, Respiratory Challenge, Metabolic Cages, Biomarkers, Pathology. Lines will be archived in the EMMA archive free-of-charge.

Outreach to new users:

The offered services for Transnational Access were displayed on the public INFRAFRONTIER website at www.infrafrontier.eu and were also advertised through INFRAFRONTIER customer mailing lists and public internet discussion groups such as the MGI-list, transgenic-list and the ISTT-list. For the phenotyping service two calls were published. Efforts were made to find new users, particularly SMEs. The number of transnational users at MRC Harwell were maintained as a result of this proposal. MRC Harwell has no other funding stream to provide Transnational Access to analyse the mutant mice from individual research groups. The usual access provided is to data

resulting from the comprehensive phenotyping of knock-out mouse lines in the IMPC project which is made freely available as a resource to researchers worldwide. This provision of access to EU researchers gave them a competitive advantage over other researchers who will not have access to such comprehensive phenotyping.

Review procedure under this proposal:

The **INFRAFRONTIER Evaluation Committee** assessed applications for the mouse first line phenotyping service offered by the WP8 Transnational Access activity. **Evaluation** of all service requests received were based on descriptions of proposed projects involving the mouse mutant line to be analysed by the first line phenotyping. In addition to excellence and scientific merit the selection panel ensured that free-of-charge access to INFRAFRONTIER2020 services were granted with priority to users who have not previously benefited from this scheme.

Overview of Applications

TA call website: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/late-onset-systemic-phenotyping-ageing-pipeline>

Total number of applications: 17

Gender distribution: 65% male; 35% female

Selected Applications

Victor Tybulewicz, Francis Crick Institute, UK

Gene of interest	Dp(16Lipi-Zbtb21)1TybEmcf (Dp1Tyb)
<p>Dp1Tyb mouse model of Down Syndrome</p> <p>Down Syndrome is caused by trisomy of human chromosome 21 (Hsa21), which affects around 1 in 750 births world-wide. DS is characterised by a large spectrum of phenotypes, which vary in severity and penetrance. All people with DS show learning difficulties and muscle hypotonia, and a subset can also present with phenotypes such as congenital heart defects, Alzheimer’s disease or leukaemia. These phenotypes result from increased dosage of one or more of the 300 or so genes on Hsa21. A full understanding of the pathology of DS requires that we identify the dosage-sensitive genes on Hsa21 that contribute to specific DS phenotypes, and elucidate how increased dosage of these genes results in the observed symptoms. Interestingly, it has been suggested that some aspects of the Syndrome may be caused by premature ageing, or premature senescence of stem cells (Adorno et al., 2013), and Alzheimer’s disease becomes evident in the Down Syndrome population with age (Wiseman et al., 2015). The majority of Hsa21 is orthologous to a region of mouse chromosome 16 (Mmu16), with the remainder having orthology to Mmu10 and Mmu17. To understand the molecular genetics of DS we have generated a novel mouse strain Dp(16Lipi-Zbtb21)1TybEmcf (Dp1Tyb) which has a duplication of the entire 22.9Mb region of Mmu16 orthologous to Hsa21, thereby increasing the dosage of about 233 genes from 2 to 3 copies (Lana-Elola et al., 2016).</p> <p>Within our own group and in close collaboration with Elizabeth Fisher (UCL) we are focussing on detailed analysis of a small number of specific phenotypes in these mice, including embryonic cardiac development, motor function and neurodegeneration. As a complement to this, the Dp1Tyb strain has also been phenotyped within the IMPC at MRC Harwell through a broad phenotyping pipeline, including a behavioural pipeline (supported by Infrafrontier 13). Dp1Tyb mice and matched controls were analysed at 9-16 weeks of age in 24 different procedures, measuring 284 parameters. The results showed significant phenotypes in 83 parameters, including heart function, skull shape, locomotor activity and sleep patterns. Since a number of phenotypes in Down Syndrome are age-related, especially neurodegeneration, we believe it would be very valuable to now extend this IMPC-type analysis to older mice, at 52-59 weeks of age as proposed by Infrafrontier 2020. Importantly, we have recently discovered a neurodegenerative phenotype in the mice – a progressive loss of motor neurons. Thus, we already have evidence of phenotypes that worsen with age. The Dp1Tyb mouse colony is currently breeding at MRC Harwell, so mice for this analysis could be generated immediately.</p> <p>Analysis of ageing mice, using such a broad phenotyping pipeline is beyond the scope of what we are able to do in our own groups. It is certainly possible this broad phenotyping pipeline may uncover novel phenotypes in aged Dp1Tyb mice, which were not visible in the younger cohort.</p> <p>In addition to the Dp1Tyb strain, we have generated a number of smaller duplications in Mmu16 of regions orthologous to Hsa21 (mouse strains Dp2Tyb – Dp9Tyb) (Lana-Elola</p>	

et al., 2016). These mouse strains are also being phenotyped within the IMPC pipelines at the younger age (9-16 weeks) in order to map the location of genes causing phenotypes in Dp1Tyb mice. As an extension of this, if novel phenotypes are found in the older Dp1Tyb cohort, a similar mapping strategy could be employed with the Dp2Tyb – DP9Tyb strains to map the location of causative genes.

Analysis of the ageing Dp1Tyb strain will be of interest to a broad range of researchers working on the genetics of DS. To our knowledge other mouse models of DS have not been subjected to a similar broad phenotyping pipeline either at young or old ages.

References

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Lana-Elola, E., Watson-Scales, S., Slender, A., Gibbins, D., Martineau, A., Douglas, C., Mohun, T., Fisher, E.M., and Tybulewicz, V. (2016). Genetic dissection of Down syndrome-associated congenital heart defects using a new mouse mapping panel. *eLife* 5, 10.7554/eLife.11614.

Wiseman, F.K., Al-Janabi, T., Hardy, J., Karmiloff-Smith, A., Nizetic, D., Tybulewicz, V.L., Fisher, E.M., and Strydom, A. (2015). A genetic cause of Alzheimer disease: mechanistic insights from Down syndrome. *Nat Rev Neurosci* 16, 564-574.

Lee Mulderrig, MRC Lab of Molecular Biology, UK

Gene of interest	Adh5 / Csb1
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Cockayne Syndrome (CS) is a rare disorder characterized by hypersensitivity to UV, growth failure, cachexia, accelerated ageing and progressive neurological defects. The genes mutated in this disease (specifically *CSA* and *CSB*) are known to play a role in the transcription-coupled nucleotide excision repair (TC-NER) DNA repair pathway (3). Although much is known about the DNA repair pathway that is disrupted in CS, little is known about what causes the DNA damage in the first place. We want to establish the source of DNA damage that is driving the CS phenotype, opening up the possibility of reducing the burden of damage at the source. This would have huge health implications for CS patients and may also highlight factors that could contribute to accelerated ageing and neurological defects in the wider population.

In the search for endogenous sources of DNA damage, recent work in our lab has focused on naturally produced aldehydes. These simple organic molecules are generated within our own cells and are also very reactive towards DNA. We speculated that the burden of endogenously generated aldehydes might be sufficient to cause DNA damage. To test this genetically in mice, we disrupted genes involved in aldehyde clearance (*Aldh2* or *Adh5*, the enzymes responsible for detoxifying acetaldehyde and formaldehyde, respectively) and combined this with the inactivation of DNA repair. The original work in our lab was focused on the Fanconi Anemia DNA repair pathway. Fanconi Anemia (FA) results from a defect in the repair of DNA interstrand crosslinks and is characterized by bone marrow failure, a strong cancer predisposition and developmental defects. In both cases, *Aldh2*^{-/-}*Fancd2*^{-/-} and *Adh5*^{-/-}*Fancd2*^{-/-} mice had a catastrophic phenotype and recapitulated the features of human FA patients. This strong genetic interaction showed that the levels of endogenous aldehydes were sufficient to cause DNA damage and drive the FA phenotype. They also led to the two-

tier protection model where the first tier protects against DNA damage by detoxifying harmful aldehydes and the second tier repairs damaged DNA (2,5,6).

Aldehydes are highly reactive and have the ability to cause many DNA lesions. They can form highly toxic interstrand crosslinks, the lesion repaired by the Fanconi Anemia pathway. However, they also have the ability to cause intrastrand crosslinks (4). This type of lesion is of interest because it is the canonical substrate for NER. We therefore wanted to ask the question of whether endogenous formaldehyde could drive the CS phenotype.

Initially, we set out to see if mouse cells lacking NER were sensitive to formaldehyde treatment, indeed the *Csb*^{-/-} cells proved to be hypersensitive. This led us to knock out *Adh5* in the *Csb* deficient background, which further sensitised cells to formaldehyde (Fig 1a). This suggested that *Csb* can repair formaldehyde-derived DNA damage so we set out to test genetically whether formaldehyde can drive the CS phenotype by breeding mice deficient in both *Adh5* and *Csb*. To date, we have been able to generate a few double knock out (DKO) mice and the results so far are suggestive of an interaction, particularly in the brain. The mice are born at reduced Mendelian ratios (Fig 1b) and show growth retardation compared to controls (Fig 1c). Around the age of 45 weeks, DKO mice start to develop abnormal gait, signs of ataxia and kyphosis (a curvature of the spine associated with accelerated aging, Fig 1d). We believe that these phenotypes may be due to the progressive neurodegeneration also seen in CS patients (but not observed in *Csb*^{-/-} mice). However, our mouse facility lacks the tools and equipment to properly assess, characterize and quantify neurological defects in mice.

We would like to apply for a comprehensive late onset phenotyping of the *Adh5*^{-/-}*Csb*^{-/-} strain along with single *Adh5*^{-/-}, *Csb*^{-/-} and wild type controls. We believe that the data generated from the phenotyping pipeline will shine light onto the nature of the neurodegeneration in these mice and might uncover other clinical symptoms associated with accelerated aging. Our results so far show that *Adh5*^{-/-}*Csb*^{-/-} mice recapitulate features of CS and suggest that formaldehyde-derived DNA damage is an important driver of aging. If this is true then it is conceivable that by quenching the free formaldehyde in CS patients the phenotype could be alleviated.

[REMOVED DUE TO CONCERN OVER UNPUBLISHED DATA]

Figure 1 – Evidence of an interaction between CSB and ADH5

a) Transformed MEF colony survival assay, cells were exposed to formaldehyde for 2 hours before plating. b) Mendelian ratios for mice born from an *ADH5*^{-/-} *CSB* +/- cross, mice were genotyped at P21. c) Plot of body weights from *CSB*^{-/-} *ADH5*^{-/-}, *ADH5*^{-/-}, and *CSB*^{-/-} males and females, WT weights were taken from the JAX website. d) The age of onset of ataxia in *CSB*^{-/-} *ADH5*^{-/-} double knock out mice.

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Although we have already made preliminary observations, these lack the quantification that the phenotyping tests at MRC Harwell could provide. We have had previous success in working with phenotyping pipelines, in 2011 the *Slx4* mouse strain was phenotyped in collaboration with the Sanger Institute and resulted in publication at Nature Genetics (1). We hope that this new proposed project will have a similar impact in the wider scientific community.

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Misa Hirose, University of Lubeck, Germany

Gene of interest	Mitochondrially-encoded ATP synthase 8 (<i>mt-Atp8</i>), and nicotinamide adenine dehydrogenase (<i>Nnt</i>)
<p>Title: Impact of mitochondrial DNA mutations on inflammaging</p> <p>Inflammaging refers to the chronic, low-grade inflammation that occurs with advanced age without overt infection. Inflammaging is a highly significant risk factor for both morbidity and mortality in elderly people because inflammation contribute to the pathogenesis of most age-related diseases¹. The etiology of Inflammaging and its potential causal role in contributing to adverse health outcomes remains largely unknown, thus the identification of pathways involved age-related inflammation across multiple systems is crucial to identify novel therapeutic intervention, and to this end, to promote health-span for the elderly².</p> <p>Mitochondria are organelles that act as the center of cellular metabolism by producing energy in the form of ATP. They consist of more than one thousand proteins, that are encoded by both nuclear and mitochondrial genomes³. The latter, in short the mtDNA, is circular, approximately 16 kilo-base in size, has hundreds to thousands of copies per cell and encodes 37 genes: 13 OXPHOS proteins, 22 tRNA and two rRNA⁴. Mutations in the mtDNA were reportedly associated with cancer, chronic inflammatory diseases, metabolic disorders, autoimmunity as well as aging^{5,6}.</p> <p>Our group and collaborators have previously reported that mice carrying a single mutation in <i>mt-Atp8</i> (e.g. C57BL/6J-mtFVB/NJ) in mtDNA exhibited an increased susceptibility to a panel of age-related chronic inflammatory conditions, including arthritis⁷, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis⁸ and atherosclerosis (unpublished data). Those phenotypes are associated with an enhanced inflammatory response, not only involving effector T cells, but also regulatory T (Treg) cells⁹⁻¹¹.</p> <p>Recently it has been reported that immunometabolism, i.e. the cellular metabolic niche determines the fate of immune cells. For example, naïve T cells differentiate into effector cells under high-glucose dependent metabolism, while de novo fatty acid synthesis promotes naïve T cells differentiation into Treg cells^{12,13}. Furthermore, the</p>	

role of mitochondria in immunity has been receiving more attention than before because of their bioenergetic capacity¹⁴. Indeed our preliminary data show that cellular functions (proliferation, cytokine production) as well as cellular metabolism (OXPHOS respiration and glycolysis) in T cells in the C57BL/6J- mtFVB/NJ compared with those in C57BL/6J wild-type mice. Furthermore, the metabolites profile in the liver obtained from C57BL/6J-mtFVB/NJ was significantly altered⁸. These experimental data indicate that the *mt-Atp8* mutation causes the skewed systemic metabolites as well as cellular metabolism, which may further may shape the T cell subset composition, thereby resulting in increased inflammatory response upon immunological or metabolic stimuli which occur in aging. Therefore, we hypothesize that the *mt-Atp8* mutation modulates T cell subpopulation by altering the cellular and systemic metabolism.

The crosstalk between mtDNA and nDNA is also shown to contribute aging-phenotypes and lifespan in mice¹⁵. In this line we would like to examine the impact of the different genetic background on the *mt-Atp8* mutation, more specifically, the effect of the nicotinamide nucleotide transhydrogenase (*Nnt*) on the mutation. Previous studies showed that two conplastic mouse strains carrying essentially the same mutations in mtDNA differed their lifespan; mice with C57BL/6 background carrying a mutation (deletion) and lacking NNT protein lived significantly longer than the mice with C57BL/6 background which does not carry the *Nnt* mutation^{16,17}, suggesting the *Nnt* mutation negates the effects of mtDNA mutations on lifespan. We recently generated another conplastic mouse strain carrying the *mt-Atp8* mutation with C57BL/6N nuclear background, without carrying the *Nnt* mutation (C57BL/6N-mtFVB/NJ).

Using our unique resources as above-mentioned (C57BL/6J-mtFVB/NJ, C57BL/6N-mtFVB/NJ and their respective wild-type strains), we plan to explore the impact of a single mutation (m.7778G>T) in mitochondrially- encoded ATPase 8 (*mt-Atp8*) in complex V on T cell subtype (regulatory and effector T cells) at different life stages, i.e. young (9-16 weeks old) and aged (52-59 weeks of age) in peripheral and central immune tissues. More specifically, we will dissect the composition, cellular metabolic phenotypes and metabolites profiles in conplastic mouse strains carrying the *mt-Atp8* mutation and their wild-type control. We will also evaluate the impact of mito-nuclear genome interaction on immune phenotyping. The levels of systemic cellular infiltration in tissues (liver, heart, muscle and white adipose tissue) will be evaluated by immunohistochemistry. To this end we plan to elucidate if a single point mutation in the mtDNA can act as a causal factor in inflammaging.

Experimental design:

1. A conplastic mouse strain C57BL/6J-mt^{FVB/NJ} (*mt-Atp8* mutant strain carrying a NNT mutation), C57BL6/J (wild-type carrying the NNT mutation), C57BL/6N-mt^{FVB/NJ} (*mt-Atp8* mutant strain without the NNT mutation) and C57BL/6N (wild-type without the NNT mutation) will be used in this study.

a. Phenotyping will be performed at 3 (young) and 12 months (aged) of age.

2. Detailed immune phenotyping of T cell subpopulations in conplastic mice

a. Composition of T cell subpopulation in peripheral and central immunological organs using flow cytometry, i.e. Th1, Th2 and Th17 effector and regulatory T cells in peripheral blood, thymus, spleen and lymph nodes)

3. Metabolite analysis in T cell subpopulation

1. Cellular metabolism evaluation using Seahorse cellular flux analyzer in T cell subpopulation (i.e. oxygen consumption, glycolysis, and fatty acid oxidation)
2. Gene/protein expression of glucose transporter (Glut1) and fatty-acid oxidation (Cpt1) by RT-PCR and western blotting
3. Metabolites analysis of regulatory T cells using mass spectrometry (performed by Mass Spectrometry Laboratory in Bioanalytic Core Facility, Center of Brain, behavior and metabolism in University of Luebeck)

4. Transcriptome analysis of regulatory T cells by RNA-Seq (commercial service will be used) to identify pathways involved in mtDNA-mutations induced inflammaging

5. Evaluation of cellular infiltration (Th1, Th2, Th17 and Treg cells) in organs (liver, heart, muscle, white adipose tissue, brain and lung) by immunohistochemistry

All methods described above are routinely performed in the group (otherwise specified above), and access to the Seahorse cellular flux analyzer is secured.

Obtained data will be systematically analyzed by linking to phenotypes that will be delivered from the phenotyping service for each target organs, as summarized in **Table 1**.

1.

T cell subpopulation (composition, metabolites, and RNA-seq)	Blood count (offered)	Clinical blood chemistry (young, offered; aged, in-house)	Histopathology (offered) +Immunohistochemistry	Phenotyping data (offered)
			Liver/WAT	Calorimetry Body composition Body weight ipGTT X-ray (liver size)
Heart	ECG, Echo X-ray (heart size) Heart weight			
Muscle	Grip test Body composition			
Brain	Open field Chronic social defeat Light/Dark box X-ray (brain size) Auditory Brain Stem Response			
Eyes (including optic nerve)	Optical coherence tomography Eye morphology			
Lung	Challenge Whole Body Plethysmography X-ray			

References

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M. Albert Basson, King's College London, UK

Gene of interest	<i>Chd8</i>																									
<p>The <i>CHD8</i> (Chromodomain Helicase DNA binding protein 8) gene was originally identified as a negative regulator of the WNT signaling pathway during development [1]. <i>CHD8</i> encodes an ATP-dependent chromatin remodeling factor [2]. <i>Chd8</i>^{-/-} mouse embryos die during early gestation as a result of cell cycle exit and apoptosis due to de-repression of p53-regulated genes [3].</p> <p>Recent exome sequencing studies on autism simplex families have led to the identified of de novo likely gene disrupting mutations in <i>CHD8</i> in several autism probands [4]. These mutations appear to be exclusively associated with affected individuals. <i>CHD8</i> is therefore one of the highest confidence autism risk genes identified to date.</p> <p>We have recently generated a new <i>Chd8</i>^{+/-} mouse model. Juvenile and young adults have been extensively phenotyped in autism-related behavioural assays and no evidence for typical autism-like behaviours were found. Instead, a number of anomalous behaviours that include an increased interest in social cues and general hypo-activity were seen (http://biorxiv.org/content/early/2017/06/20/143552). We hypothesise that <i>Chd8</i> may be important in several late onset, age-related conditions, which include cancer and neurological conditions like Parkinson's disease and dementia.</p>																										
<p>Cancer: As a negative regulator of WNT signaling [5], <i>CHD8</i> mutation is likely to have a role as a driver or promoter of cancers that arise as a result of WNT pathway hyper-activation. The most notable of these is colorectal cancers [6]. Mutations in <i>CHD8</i> are prevalent in a large number of cancers, which include colorectal, stomach and ovarian cancers (Fig. 1).</p>																										
<p>The chart displays the alteration frequency of <i>CHD8</i> across 50 different cancer types. The y-axis represents the alteration frequency from 0% to 14%. The x-axis lists the cancer types. The bars are stacked by alteration type: Mutation (green), Deletion (blue), Amplification (red), and Multiple alterations (grey). Arrows point to Colorectal, Stomach, and Ovarian cancers. A legend at the bottom identifies the alteration types.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Cancer type</th> <th>Mutation (%)</th> <th>Deletion (%)</th> <th>Amplification (%)</th> <th>Multiple alterations (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>Colorectal adenocarcinoma</td><td>9.0</td><td>0.0</td><td>0.0</td><td>0.0</td></tr> <tr><td>Stomach adenocarcinoma</td><td>8.0</td><td>1.0</td><td>0.0</td><td>0.0</td></tr> <tr><td>Ovarian serous cystadenocarcinoma</td><td>5.0</td><td>0.0</td><td>5.0</td><td>0.0</td></tr> <tr><td>Other cancer types</td><td>0.0 - 8.0</td><td>0.0 - 2.0</td><td>0.0 - 4.0</td><td>0.0 - 1.0</td></tr> </tbody> </table>		Cancer type	Mutation (%)	Deletion (%)	Amplification (%)	Multiple alterations (%)	Colorectal adenocarcinoma	9.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	Stomach adenocarcinoma	8.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	Ovarian serous cystadenocarcinoma	5.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	Other cancer types	0.0 - 8.0	0.0 - 2.0	0.0 - 4.0	0.0 - 1.0
Cancer type	Mutation (%)	Deletion (%)	Amplification (%)	Multiple alterations (%)																						
Colorectal adenocarcinoma	9.0	0.0	0.0	0.0																						
Stomach adenocarcinoma	8.0	1.0	0.0	0.0																						
Ovarian serous cystadenocarcinoma	5.0	0.0	5.0	0.0																						
Other cancer types	0.0 - 8.0	0.0 - 2.0	0.0 - 4.0	0.0 - 1.0																						
<p>Figure 1: Frequency of <i>CHD8</i> mutations found in a variety of cancers. Note the high frequency (9%) of mutation in colorectal cancers, mutation and deletion in stomach and amplification in ovarian cancers.</p>																										

Given these findings, we would predict that *Chd8*^{+/-} mice would have an increased risk for developing certain cancers, in particular those of the digestive tract.

Late onset neurological conditions:

During the course of our analysis of brain development in *Chd8*-deficient mice, we performed several RNA-seq analyses. Gene set enrichment analyses on genes differentially expressed in *Chd8*-deficient neocortices during development, revealed striking enrichment for genes implicated in Parkinson's disease (KEGG pathway, $p=1.7 \times 10^{-5}$), Alzheimer's disease (KEGG, $p=6.6 \times 10^{-5}$).

Based on these findings, we would predict that these animals may have a genetic predisposition to developing motor and cognitive deficits during ageing.

7

In summary, the *Chd8*^{+/-} mouse line is an important model to include in the Infrafrontier2020 late onset phenotyping project.

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Raffaele Teperino, Helmholtz Center Munich, Germany

Gene of interest	<i>Eed</i> (<i>Embryonic Ectoderm Development</i>)
<p>Polycomb (PcG) proteins modify chromatin architecture to mediate gene silencing. Two major multiprotein complexes constitute the PcG system. The Polycomb Repressive Complex 2 (PRC2), whose enzymatic components catalyze mono- di- and tri-methylation of the histone 3 lysine 27 (H3K27)(1, 2); and Polycomb Repressive Complex 1 (PRC1), which recognises the PRC2-deposited H3K27me3 mark and promotes further silencing via the ubiquitination of the lysine 119 on the histone H2A(3).</p> <p>PcG proteins control a plethora of cellular processes, from proliferation and differentiation to maintenance of cell identity, stability of transcriptional programs and cancer development. Most interestingly for this program, PcG proteins regulate cellular senescence by repressing the expression of the <i>Ink4a</i> locus, master regulator of cellular proliferation and senescence (4, 5). Of note, PcG- dependent H3K27me3 is a common characteristic of metabolically relevant genes (6). These findings suggest a central role for PcG and PcG-target genes in cellular homeostasis.</p> <p><i>Eed</i> - Embryonic Ectoderm Development - is the docking component of the PRC2 complex and is crucial for proper assembly and enzymatic activity of both PRC1 and PRC2 complexes(7-9). Due to its essential function in development, <i>Eed</i> homozygous mutant mice are embryonic lethal(10), and tissue-specific deletion has been associated to different abnormalities of the hematopoietic system(11-13), loss of intestinal stem cells(14), and spermatogenic defects(15). Also, unpublished data from the applicant</p>	

indicate a strong tissue specificity of Eed action. Indeed, Beta-cell specific KO mice develop lethal type 1 diabetes as a consequence of beta-cells dedifferentiation (Lu,... Teperino, et al. unpublished); while liver specific KO feature improved metabolic control (Teperino et al. unpublished).

Given the aforementioned evidence, what intrigues us is how Eed would sentence organismal phenotypic trajectories. The easiest approach to this question is to interrogate whole body heterozygote animals (KO are lethal) and follow them for development of early and late-onset phenotypes. Eed^{+/-} mice are viable and breed normally. Interestingly enough, preliminary analysis of a small cohort of young mutants indicates that Eed^{+/-} mice are overweight (Fig.1), a prelude to early development of metabolic phenotypes. We expect these mice to show accelerated ageing and ageing associated phenotypes, that only an unbiased, systemic phenotyping pipeline can highlight. As a complement to the systemic phenotyping, affected tissues will undergo a molecular workup including transcriptome (RNA-Seq); chromatin architecture (ATAC-Seq) and chromatin state (ChIP-Seq) analyses. The resulting set of data will constitute an unprecedented molecular and phenotypic characterization of the in vivo role of PcG in organismal ageing.

Fig.1 – Body weight curve in Eed^{+/-} mice (colored line) compared to standard, age-matched, C57BL6/J mice.

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Outcomes

Applicant	Customer contacted	Importation / cohort breeding	Phenotyping started	Phenotyping completed
Tybulewicz	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mulderrig/Patel	✓	✓	✓	✓
Hirose	✓	✓	✓	✓
Basson	✓	✓	✓	✓
Teperino	✓	✓	✓	✓

Outlook

The user projects that were selected contained difficult/complex elements in their execution. These projects would normally not be taken up by commercial services and would only be possible by extensive collaboration in an academic setting. By successfully completing these projects, MRC Harwell Institute (Mary Lyon Centre) WP8 demonstrated the robustness and flexibility of their phenotyping pipeline. These features favour the adoption of this pilot service into a sustainable and attractive INFRAFRONTIER service going forward.

Hidden costs

Some of the hidden costs that need to be considered to up-scale this access call to a full-fledged service are mentioned below:

ADH5-CSB1 double knockout

- Did not survive in expected ratio when bred from double heterozygous intercross.
- Double homozygotes could not be used for breeding.
- Controls and experimental groups could not be bred from the same matings. Therefore, needed more complex breeding and control strategies.

Mt-ATP8

- Initially planned to rederive two lines with the same mitochondrial mutations on C57BL/6N and C57BL/6J. However, design changed to breed mitochondrial mutation onto NNT null background as it would more clearly answer the experimental question.
- Phenotyping cohort bred from different matings in order to have some with and some without the mitochondrial mutation, in the presence or absence of NNT.

TS1-TYB

- Did not survive in mendelian ratios. Welfare difficulties including craniofacial abnormalities impacting teeth and prevalence of hydrocephalus. Close observation and additional welfare monitoring were needed.

Stand-alone dedicated INFRAFRONTIER service

In a recent survey of TA call providers, WP8 partner MRC Harwell Institute have expressed interest in adapting this pilot TA call into an independent sustainable service outside of I2020 with an expanded range of phenotyping capabilities. Their feedback also stated that the projects were scientifically challenging and can result in high-impact publications. The next steps would be to formulate a business plan for an ageing phenotyping service by incorporating the experiences from this successful pilot service.

Application Form

INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure

INFRAFRONTIER2020 Project - Trans-national Access call - May

2017

Late-onset systemic phenotyping (ageing pipeline)

Call information and application form

Context and aim of the call

INFRAFRONTIER is the European Research Infrastructure for phenotyping, archiving and distribution of model mammalian genomes. The INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure provides access to first-class tools and data for biomedical research, and thereby contributes to improving the understanding of gene function in human health and disease using the mouse model. The core services of INFRAFRONTIER comprise the systemic phenotyping of mouse mutants in the participating mouse clinics, and the archiving and distribution of mouse mutant lines by the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA) (www.infracontier.eu).

INFRAFRONTIER2020 project and ageing

The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project aims to develop pilot platforms and services supporting ageing research. These activities are tightly integrated with the current efforts of the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC, www.mousephenotype.org) to set up a standardised late-onset (ageing) pipeline. In the IMPC phase 2 a significant fraction of mutant lines will be aged and re-phenotyped to identify genes involved with late-onset disease. The INFRAFRONTIER2020 Trans-national Access call complements the highly standardised IMPC late-onset phenotyping, as existing mouse lines with different mutations and genetic backgrounds can be tested with the IMPC late-onset phenotyping pipeline.

The INFRAFRONTIER open call facilitates access for the wider biomedical research community to the unique infrastructure and scientific expertise of the MRC Harwell mouse clinic. A total of four mouse mutant lines can be tested through a broad based late-onset phenotyping pipeline in all the major adult organ systems and most areas of major human disease and will be re-phenotyped at a later stage (weeks 52-59). Access to the service will be granted on the basis of scientific excellence and supports the development and in-depth characterisation of mouse models for research on ageing and age-related diseases. INFRAFRONTIER will provide open access to all tested mouse lines and their phenotyping data.

The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project has received funding from the EU Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (H2020-EU.1.4.1.1. Developing new world class research infrastructures)

Trans-national Access (TA) activity of the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project Free of charge mouse late-onset phenotyping service / Access modalities

- The EC Horizon 2020 funded INFRAFRONTIER2020 project (2017 – 2020) supports eligible customers with a free of charge mouse **late-onset phenotyping service** implemented as a Trans-national Access activity providing a total of 4 access units.
- The **access unit** offered covers the production of a cohort and a comprehensive first line phenotyping. The **phenotyping will be performed at two different ages so that late onset of disease can be measured and / or the progression of disease with age.**
- **Mutant mouse lines will be provided by the selected applicants either as breeding pairs or frozen embryos or sperm.** MRC Harwell will breed the cohorts required for the pipelines, use the IMPC late-onset phenotyping pipeline and perform any relevant additional tests. Health status requirements to accept animals will be provided.
- The **phenotyping data will be made publicly available** through a phenotyping database or as a phenotyping report. Successful applicants must submit phenotyped mouse mutant lines to the **EMMA repository**. An **optional grace period** of up to one year can be granted before data and mutant mouse lines must be released.
- **Costs:** The access to the INFRAFRONTIER2020 phenotyping service is free of charge. However, the shipment cost of the starting material (breeding pairs or frozen embryos) to the MRC Harwell mouse clinic must be covered by the customers.
- **Eligibility:** The INFRAFRONTIER2020 **Trans-national Access call is open** and proposals can be submitted from applicants around the world. Three projects must be allocated to applicants from EU Member States and Associated Countries, and one project can be allocated to applicants from third countries.
- **Application:** Service requests for the INFRAFRONTIER2020 mouse phenotyping service can be made via this **application form**. Applications for the Trans-national Access activity must include a short description of the project involving the mouse mutant being phenotyped by the INFRAFRONTIER2020 TA service.
- **Selection procedure:** Proposals from eligible customers for free of charge access to the INFRAFRONTIER2020 mouse phenotyping service will be subject to a review procedure. The review will be based on short descriptions of the projects involving the mouse mutants that will be phenotyped by the TA service. A mixed panel of members of INFRAFRONTIER and of an external Evaluation Committee will assess service requests supported by the TA activity. In addition to scientific merit of applicants, soundness of the proposal, relevance for ageing research and feasibility will be assessed. Applicants will be informed on the outcome of the evaluation within 6 weeks after the end of the call for which the TA application was submitted.

- **Acknowledgements:** Please do acknowledge any support under this scheme in all resulting publications with "Part of this work has been funded by the European Union Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (Grant Agreement Number 730879)

Support offered

MRC Harwell will provide Trans-national Access to researchers across Europe to submit mouse lines to their comprehensive phenotyping service. Four researchers will be able to use this Trans-national Access which builds upon the research performed in the EC-funded EUMODIC and INFRAFRONTIER-I3 projects. The centre is fully equipped with state-of-the-art research instrumentation to facilitate comprehensive phenotypic analyses covering a wide range of physiological functions ranging from cardiovascular, neuro-behaviour and metabolism expertise to detailed pathology assessments. Routinely, all phenotyping activities are performed in a high-throughput fashion, as a service to support internal programs or for the wider scientific community.

MRC Harwell is a partner in the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) and currently performs first-line phenotyping of around 140 lines per year. This is funded by the UK MRC and the NIH. Phenotyping is performed according to the standardised SOPs within an agreed pipeline of tests. The tests and pipeline for the late-onset phenotyping is currently being agreed by the IMPC. The proposed ageing pipeline is shown below. The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project opens up new areas to users, in that phenotyping will be performed at later ages allowing exploration of late-onset disease. There are few laboratories equipped to offer this comprehensive phenotyping and access to it at later ages makes it a unique access. Users will benefit from access to the infrastructure and technical expertise of the MRC Harwell mouse clinic. In addition, they will be given support by MRC Harwell to analyse and interpret the results. MRC Harwell will also suggest additional phenotyping tests that they can do to further describe the phenotypes.

Description of the phenotyping pipeline

In general, the provided 1st line phenotyping pipeline will be based on the IMPC pipeline for adult mutant mice as described at <http://www.mousephenotype.org/>. The standard pipeline may be adjusted during the course of the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project.

IMPC late onset phenotyping pipeline

Application Form - INFRAFRONTIER2020 mouse late-onset systemic phenotyping call

Closing of call on June 30th - Evaluation process from July 1st - August 15th

First name	
Family name	
Email	
Phone	
Fax	
Institution	
Address	
Town	
Postcode	
Country	
Link to lab website	
Link to publication list	

**The following data is required by the EC for statistical purposes.
Applications can only be considered if all data are provided.**

Gender	
Birth year	
Nationality	
Researcher status (e.g. Prof, Postdoc)	
Scientific background	

Description of proposed project

Please describe briefly the proposed project involving the mouse mutant line to be analyzed by a comprehensive late-onset phenotyping in the MRC Harwell mouse clinic. This proposal will be the foundation for the evaluation of your project.

Gene of interest	

Please, do not extend beyond the provided space (max 2 pages including references)

Send your proposal to proposals@infrafrontier.eu by June 30th 2017

[INFRAFRONTIER2020 project description](#)

INFRAFRONTIER2020 - Towards enduring mouse resources and services advancing research into human health and disease

INFRAFRONTIER2020 objectives

The INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure integrates European Mouse Clinics and the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA) with the common goal to ensure access to mouse models for basic research of human health and disease, and to translate this knowledge into therapeutic approaches for the benefit of the European society.

The expanded INFRAFRONTIER2020 network, coordinated by the INFRAFRONTIER GmbH, includes 3 SMEs and is strategically responding to the INFRADEV3 call with aligned objectives to advance the long-term sustainability which are **1)** development of business models and a stable legal framework; **2)** raise awareness of the INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure; **3)** provide bespoke services aligned with user demands; **4)** promote best practices in mouse phenogenomics; **5)** enhance robustness of the INFRAFRONTIER IT infrastructure and use of the EMMA strain resource; and **6)** improve business processes. Towards achieving these objectives key INFRAFRONTIER2020 project deliverables are:

- INFRAFRONTIER Business Plan2.0, and business models for all services
- Stable legal framework built on the INFRAFRONTIER legal entity
- INFRAFRONTIER annual stakeholder conferences
- Customised mouse model and secondary phenotyping pilot services

- INFRAFRONTIER advanced training schools in mouse phenogenomics
- Reengineered EMMA Database2.0 system
- Annotated mouse models of human diseases
- Quality management system for the legal entity

INFRAFRONTIER2020 will **1)** enhance the sustainable operation of the INFRAFRONTIER RI; **2)** continue to structure the ERA, **3)** foster innovation, and **4)** address major societal challenges in human health by customised service pilots supporting research into common and rare diseases. A sustainable INFRAFRONTIER RI will ensure the quality of deposited mice and support the reproducibility of biological results. Outreach efforts will raise awareness of resources and services and facilitate sustainable engagement with industry and global consortia such as the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium

The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project has received funding from the EU Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (H2020-EU.1.4.1.1. Developing new world class research infrastructures)
